

Arthropod abundance in continuous vs biannual rice cropping systems

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With year-round irrigation, a continuous rice cropping pattern popularly termed a *rice garden* offers maximum utilization of land. If the field area is less than 1.5 ha 4 crops of early maturing rice/ year can be grown, using family labor, by dividing the field into 13 plots, transplanted sequentially each week. Because rice is found in all growth stages at any one time, continuous cropping would appear ideal for insect pest buildup. We measured populations of both insect pests and natural enemies without insecticide protection over 2 years (1978-79) at IRRI using insect- susceptible cultivars (IR1917 in 1978 and IET 3877 in 1979) in continuous (0.25-ha field) and biannual (0.5-ha field) systems.

We hypothesized three possible consequences of continuous cropping in terms of insect pest population buildup:

1. Continuous cropping would nullify the inherent cultural control offered by biannual cropping to break pest population cycles. Pest populations would multiply to epidemic numbers more rapidly than in the biannual system.
2. There would be no significant change in pest abundance due to continuous cropping because insect pests could successfully span the periods between the biannual crops through migration from nearby fields planted at different times.
3. Pest populations would decline in continuous plantings because of a newly-found favorable advantage offered to natural enemies whose population build-up had previously been selectively held back in biannual croppings (perhaps through a lower capability to migrate).

The precedent for this statement comes from the well-documented fact that, biological control is more successful on perennial than on annual crops, and continuous cropping is similar to a perennial crop. Each group of insect pests may to be highly successful migrants, may respond differently to continuous cropping. Whorl maggot and rice bug, which have definite preferences for specific stages of rice, may greatly increase in continuous cropping. Brown and white-backed planthoppers, which are believed to already have attained their biotic potential in biannual cropping systems. The wide array of stem borer and leaf folder larval parasites currently known, but considered ineffective, may become highly abundant to check these pests. Insect pest populations were highly similar over four cropping seasons in continuous and biannual cropping systems (Table 1). They were generally low in both systems — only whorl maggot and stem borers exceeded economic injury levels during the 2 years.

Stem borers were more abundant in continuous plantings. The differences over seasons, however, were neither great nor highly consistent. Natural enemies of hoppers — spiders and egg parasites — were abundant in both systems (Table 1). Spider numbers were greater than the combined populations of plant hoppers and leafhoppers. The differences in hopper egg parasitization between cropping systems were not striking.

Parasitization estimates of the other pests over the 2-year period were more difficult to make because the pest populations were generally low (Table 2). Parasitization estimates of leaf folder larvae and yellow stem borer eggs were almost identical in both systems. Parasitization of rice bug eggs was low, but was greater in continuous cropping. Conclusions regarding parasitization of stem borer larvae were difficult to make because of the low sample sizes, but biannual cropping favored yellow stem borer parasites, whereas the continuous system favored striped stem borer parasites.

Evidence from 2 years' observations of insect-susceptible cultivars without insecticide supported hypothesis 2; continuous cropping did not dramatically increase or decrease insect pest populations. Based on economic thresholds used in 1978-79, no more than two insecticide applications would have been justified (1st and 2d crops of 1978) and the application number would have been the same for both cropping systems.

Three factors regarding extrapolation of these results should be borne in mind:

1. The plots used were small and perhaps the fields surrounding the trial, which received high levels of insecticide, helped cause the low pest numbers;
2. The location of the experiment on the IRRI farm (itself a continuously cropped field) may have increased the pest populations in the biannual plot; and
3. The conclusions are limited only to insect pests.

IRRI 1978-79 ^{a/}							
Year	Crop	Pest	Stage	Individuals held (no.)		Parasitization (%)	
				Biannual	Continuous	Biannual	Continuous
1978	Second	<i>L. oratorius</i>	Egg	213	147	4	16
		<i>S. incertulas</i>	Larva	24	14	21	7
		<i>C. suppressalis</i>	Larva	24	5	8	60
		<i>C. medinalis</i>	Larva	60	73	33	29
1979	First	<i>S. incertulas</i>	Egg ^{b/}	623	734	96	95
^{a/} Unreplicated treatments. Parasitization was recorded from field plots in the continuous cropping system planted the same week as the biannual crop							
^{b/} Using Otake's exposure method							